

Child Abuse and Neglect in Media

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Introduction

Child abuse, physical, sexual, or emotional maltreatment or neglect of children by parents, guardians, or others responsible for a child’s welfare. Physical abuse is characterized by physical injury, usually inflicted as a result of a beating or inappropriately harsh discipline. Sexual abuse includes molestation, incest, rape, prostitution, or use of a child for pornographic purposes. Neglect can be physical in nature (abandonment, failure to seek needed health care), educational (failure to see that a child is attending school), or emotional (abuse of a spouse or another child in the child’s presence, allowing a child to witness adult substance abuse). Inappropriate punishment, verbal abuse, and scapegoating are also forms of emotional or psychological child abuse. Some authorities consider parental actions abusive if they have future negative consequences, e.g., exposure of a child to violence or harmful substances, extending in some views to the passive inhalation of cigarette smoke.

In practice, there are borderline areas where what constitutes child abuse is not clear. For example, the U.S. Supreme Court has ruled (1944) that parents do not have an absolute right to deny life-saving medical treatment to their children, but devout members of the Church of Christ, Scientist, and other churches believe in the healing power of prayer and do not always seek medical help. Most U.S. states, however, permit parents to use religious beliefs as a defence against prosecution for the withholding of medical treatment from their sick children, even in cases where the lack of treatment results in a child’s death.

Objectives

- The percentage of children who experience violence, exploitation, abuse, and neglect is reduced.
- The percentage of children who receive appropriate care and protection after experiencing violence, exploitation, abuse, or neglect is increased.
- The percentage of countries that ratify and implement relevant conventions or formally adopt internationally recognized principles, standards, and procedural safeguards to protect children from violence, exploitation, abuse, and neglect is increased.

Reference Design

This study is based on secondary data. Materials are collected from the newspaper, magazines, and websites.

Child Abuse: Definition

Child abuse can result from physical, emotional, or sexual harm. While child abuse is often in the form of an action, there are also examples of inaction that cause harm, such as neglect. Some households that suffer from alcoholism/substance abuse and anger issues have higher occurrences of child abuse as compared to households without. Outcomes of child abuse can result in both short and long term injury, and even death. There are some children who may be unaware that they are victims of child abuse.

- Physical abuse may involve hitting, shaking, throwing, poisoning, burning or scalding, drowning, suffocating or otherwise causing physical harm to a child. Physical harm may also be caused when a parent or caregiver fabricates the symptoms of, or deliberately induces, illness in a child.
- Emotional/psychological abuse is the persistent emotional abuse of a child such as to cause severe and persistent adverse effects on the child's emotional development. Emotional maltreatment may take the form of age or developmentally inappropriate expectations on children. It may involve conveying to children that they are worthless or unloved; not giving them opportunities to express their views or 'making fun' of what they say or how they communicate; seeing or hearing the ill-treatment of another; being seriously bullied (including cyberbullying), or exploited or corrupted. Emotional abuse is involved in all types of maltreatment, although it may occur alone. Children who are the subject of fabricated illness are also subject to emotional abuse, either as a result of being brought up in a fabricated sick role, or because of an abnormal relationship with their caregiver, or disturbed family relationships. More recently, domestic violence has been recognized as maltreatment, and is a common cause of emotional or psychological harm to children.
- Sexual abuse involves forcing or enticing a child or young person to take part in sexual activities, not necessarily involving a high level of violence, whether or not the child is aware of what is happening. Activities may involve physical contact, including assault by penetration or non-penetrative acts and non-contact activities, such as involving children in watching sexual activities, encouraging them to behave in sexually inappropriate ways, or grooming them in preparation for abuse (including via the internet). Sexual abuse is perpetrated by men and women, although the majority of sexual abuse of children is by male perpetrators against female children, typically someone known to them (i.e. a family member or family friend). Abuse by a stranger is less common. Sexual abuse can occur between children.
- Neglect is the persistent failure to meet a child's basic physical and/or psychological needs, likely to result in the serious impairment of his or her health or development. Neglect may occur during pregnancy as a result of maternal substance abuse. Once a child is born, neglect may involve a parent or caregiver failing to provide a child with adequate food, clothing and shelter (including exclusion from home or abandonment); failing to protect him or her from physical and emotional harm or danger; or failing to ensure access to appropriate medical care or treatment. It may include neglect of, or unresponsiveness to, a child's basic emotional needs.

Causes

A combination of individual, relational, community, and societal factors contribute to the risk of child maltreatment and abuse. Although children are not responsible for the harm inflicted upon them, certain individual characteristics have been found to increase their risk of being maltreated. Risk factors are contributing factors-not direct causes.

Examples of Risk Factors

- Disabilities or mental retardation in children that may increase caregiver burden
- Social isolation of families
- Parents’ lack of understanding of children’s needs and child development
- Parents’ history of domestic abuse
- Poverty and other socioeconomic disadvantages, such as unemployment
- Family disorganization, dissolution, and violence, including intimate partner violence
- Lack of family cohesion
- Substance abuse in the family
- Young, single non-biological parents
- Poor parent-child relationships and negative interactions
- Parental thoughts and emotions supporting maltreatment behaviours
- Parental stress and distress, including depression or other mental health conditions
- Community violence

Investigation

1. Any person who has reasonable cause to suspect child abuse or neglect should report the matter to Children’s Protective Services (CPS) via telephone call at once (24 hours 800 number). If in doubt, call CPS scanner who will clarify whether it is a case or not.
2. Information needed for call: Name, age, address of child, a description of the abuse or neglect, names of child’s parents, child’s guardian, or the person with whom the child resides.
3. A written report DHS-3200, Report of Actual or Suspected Child Abuse or Neglect must be filed within 72 hours by the reporting person as per Child Protection Law, Act 238, Section 3, No. 1.
4. Send written report to Protective Services in either Van Buren or Cass County. Consult resources manual for numbers.
5. A copy of the report should go in patient’s chart or the report number should be recorded in the chart.
6. The reporting person should notify the program supervisor and/or the director of nursing to review the matter. It may also be required to review cases with the Medical Director.
7. As per law, CPS is to investigate all reported cases within 24 hours of initial telephone call report.
8. Confidentiality of person reporting guaranteed by Act 238, Section 5, whereby disclosure is only with the consent of that person or by judicial process. A person acting in good faith who makes a report is immune from civil or criminal liability from child’s parents, guardian, or caretaker.
9. If a referral is received from CPS for a Public Health Nurse (PHN) to investigate a family for abuse or neglect, it will be accomplished by doing exactly what is requested and reporting back to whom they say needs the information.

Conclusion

Through early detection and reporting, dentists have the opportunity to prevent further injury or neglect to children suspected of having been maltreated. In instances where a previously abused child is returned to the environment that fostered the abuse, without any intervention (reporting or family therapy), 25% were seriously reinjured and 5% were killed. Child maltreatment is a cyclic disease with abused children often becoming abusive parents. Between 30 and 60% of abusive parents admit to being abused or neglected as a child. Ninety per cent of males in prisons were abused as a child with over 50% of violent female criminals admitting to being sexually and/or physically abused as children.

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